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Strength Comparison Between Plain Concrete and Human Hair Fiber Reinforced Concrete

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ABSTRACT

This experimental study compares the strength performance of Plain Concrete (PC) and Human Hair Fiber Reinforced Concrete (HHFRC). M20 grade concrete mixes were prepared with human hair fiber contents of 0%, 0.4%, 0.8%, and 1.6% by weight of cement while maintaining a constant water–cement ratio of 0.45. Standard cubes, cylinder, and beam specimens were cast, water cured, and tested at curing ages of 7, 14, and 28 days. Workability was evaluated using the slump test, and mechanical properties were assessed through compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength tests in accordance with relevant Indian Standard codes.

The results showed a consistent reduction in workability with increasing fiber content due to fiber interlocking and reduced flowability. Concrete containing 0.4% human hair fiber exhibited optimum performance, achieving a maximum 28-day compressive strength of 24.64 MPa, flexural strength of 5.01 MPa, and significantly improved tensile strength, with split tensile strength reaching 3.39 MPa compared to plain concrete. The inclusion of human hair fibers effectively controlled micro-crack propagation, enhanced tensile resistance, and improved post-cracking behavior. Higher fiber contents of 0.8% and 1.6% resulted in strength reduction due to poor workability and fiber clustering. Although lower strength values were observed at 14 days due to cold weather curing conditions, adequate curing ensured satisfactory strength development at 28 days. The study concludes that human hair fiber can be effectively utilized as a sustainable and low-cost reinforcement in concrete, with an optimum dosage of 0.4% by weight of cement recommended for crack-resistant and tensile-strength-enhanced applications.

Keywords: *Fiber (HHFRC), Sustainable construction materials, compressive reinforced concrete, strength, Split tensile strength, Flexural strength human hair fiber reinforced concrete*

INTRODUCTION

Concrete is one of the most extensively used construction materials worldwide due to its high compressive strength, durability, versatility, and ease of production from locally available materials. It plays a vital role in the construction of buildings, bridges, pavements, and other infrastructure systems. Despite these advantages, conventional plain concrete exhibits low tensile strength and brittle behavior under flexural and tensile stresses. This inherent weakness leads to the initiation and propagation of microcracks, which may cause sudden failure and reduce long-term durability [5].

Cracking in concrete not only affects structural safety but also facilitates the ingress of moisture and aggressive chemicals, accelerating deterioration. This issue is particularly critical in seismic-prone regions such as Nepal, where structures are subjected to cyclic loading and energy dissipation demands. Improving the ductility, crack resistance, and post cracking performance of concrete is therefore essential to enhance its structural reliability and service life.

One widely adopted solution to overcome the brittle nature of plain concrete is the incorporation of fibers into the concrete matrix, resulting in fiber reinforced concrete (FRC). Fibers are distributed randomly within the concrete act as crack bridging elements, delaying crack initiation and restricting crack propagation. This mechanism significantly improves tensile strength, flexural strength, toughness, and energy absorption capacity of concrete [2]. Various fibers such as steel, polypropylene, glass, and natural fibers

have been investigated for enhancing concrete performance.

In recent years, the use of sustainable and waste-based materials in construction have gained increasing attention. Human hair has emerged as a potential natural fiber for concrete reinforcement due to its high tensile strength, flexibility, and non-biodegradable nature. Large quantities of human hair waste are generated from salons and households, posing environmental disposal challenges. Utilizing this waste material as fiber reinforcement not only improves concrete performance but also contributes to sustainable construction practices.

Several experimental studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of human hair fibers in improving the mechanical behavior of concrete. Patil et al. (2013) reported that the inclusion of small percentages of human hair fibers enhanced crack resistance and reduced plastic shrinkage cracking, while marginal improvements were observed in tensile performance and ductility. Similarly, studies have shown that fiber reinforcement plays a significant role in controlling early-age cracking, which is a common problem in conventional concrete [1,7].

Research conducted up to April 2021 indicates that human hair fiber reinforced concrete exhibits improved split tensile and flexural strength up to an optimum fiber content, generally ranging between 1% and 1.5% by weight of cement. Beyond this optimum level, a reduction in strength is often observed due to poor workability, fiber balling, and non-uniform distribution within the concrete matrix [4].

These findings emphasize the importance of appropriate fiber dosage and mixing techniques.

Standard laboratory test methods are commonly employed to evaluate the mechanical properties of both plain and fiber in forced concrete. Compressive strength is typically determined using cube specimens at curing ages of 7, 14, and 28 days, while flexural strength is evaluated using beam specimens subjected to two-point or third point loading as specified in IS 516:1959. The 28day compressive strength is generally considered the benchmark for structural design.[3]

In seismic regions, fiber-reinforced concrete offers improved ductility and energy dissipation capacity compared to plain concrete. Pandey and Sapkota (2021) reported that while steel fibers significantly enhance flexural strength and toughness, human hair fibers are effective in controlling shrinkage cracking and improving early-stage crack resistance.[6] However, workability challenges associated with lightweight fibers such as human hair necessitate the use of chemical admixtures. The use of plasticizers and superplasticizers has been recommended to improve fiber dispersion and maintain workability without increasing water content [8].

Based on the findings of previous studies, it is evident that fiber reinforcement, particularly using sustainable materials such as human hair, can significantly improve the tensile and flexural behavior of concrete. However, comparative experimental data evaluating the strength performance of plain concrete and human hair fiber reinforced concrete under identical conditions remain limited. Therefore, the present study aims to experimentally compare the compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength characteristics of plain concrete and

human hair fiber reinforced concrete at different curing ages, with the objective of identifying an optimum fiber content suitable for practical and sustainable construction applications.

SPECIMENS DESCRIPTION

- Cube: 150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm.
- Cylinder: 150 mm x 300 mm.
- Beam: 600 mm x 150 mm x 100 mm.
- Concrete: M20

METHODOLOGY AND DATA

In this study, a series of concrete mixes were designed with human hair fiber dosages of 0%, 0.4%, 0.8%, and 1.6% by weight of cement to evaluate their effect on strength performance.

Preparation of Hair Fiber Reinforced Concrete

The required quantity of human hair fiber was calculated based on the specified percentage by weight of cement. Cement and fine aggregate were first dry mixed, after which hair fibers were gradually added to ensure uniform dispersion. Coarse aggregates were then added, followed by the addition of water to obtain workable concrete. The concrete was placed into moulds in layers and compacted using a tamping rod with not less than 25 strokes per layer. After 24 hours, the specimens were demolded and cured in clean water until the time of testing.

Materials Used

- Cement: Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of Grade 43 (Arghakhanchi Cement) with a specific gravity of 3.122. The initial and final setting times were 45 minutes and 600 minutes, respectively.
- Fine Aggregate: Locally available sand conforming to Grading Zone II, sieved through a 4.75 mm IS sieve and

washed to remove impurities. The specific gravity was 2.63.

- Coarse Aggregate: Crushed angular aggregates passing 20 mm and retained on 4.75 mm IS sieve, washed and cleaned before use. The specific gravity was 2.7.
- Human Hair: Human hair fibers collected from salons in Bhaktapur district were cleaned by separating waste materials, washing with acetone, sun drying, and sorting by length and quality before use.
- Water: Clean potable water was used for mixing and curing of concrete.

BASIC TEST RESULTS OF MATERIALS

For all the materials which are used in the project should have basic test results according to the IS specifications.

The basic test results obtained are presented below.

Basic Test Results for Cement

- Fineness of cement = 7.16%
- Specific gravity of cement = 3.15
- Normal consistency of cement = 31.5%

- Penetration depth for initial setting time = 5 mm
- Penetration depth for final setting time = 32 mm

Basic Test Results for Fine Aggregate

- Sieve analysis for fine aggregate = Zone II
- Specific gravity of fine aggregate = 2.63
- Water absorption for fine aggregate = 1.2%

Basic Test Results for Coarse Aggregate

- Sieve analysis for coarse aggregate = Conforming to Table 2 of IS383:1970
- Specific gravity of coarse aggregate = 2.7
- Water absorption for coarse aggregate = 0.5%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Compressive Strength Test

The compressive strength of concrete is determined by testing the cubes under compressive testing machine. The results of compressive strength are shown in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Results of compressive strength.

S. No.	No. of Days	Compressive Strength (MPa)			
		0%	0.4%	0.8%	1.6%
1	7	12.05	13.09	11.36	9.56
2	14	13.85	16.53	14.43	10.60
3	28	21.86	24.64	22.08	15.46

Fig. 1: Variation of hair fiber content vs compressive strength at 7,14 & 28 days.

Split Tensile Test

Split tensile strength test was conducted for the cylinders of 150mm dia. and 300mm length. The obtained values are tabulated in Table Compared to

conventional concrete. Crack width is for this fiber reinforced concrete shows bridging property. Splitting of specimens into two pieces can be controlled completely with this fiber.

Table 2: Results of split tensile strength test.

S. No.	No. of days	Split Tensile Strength (MPa)			
		0%	0.4%	0.8%	1.6%
1	7	2.71	2.91	2.86	2.38
2	14	3.02	3.23	3.07	2.74
3	28	3.20	3.39	3.39	3.39

Fig. 2: Variation of hair content vs split tensile strength at 7,14 & 28 days.

Flexural Strength Test

This test was conducted for the beams of 600mm length, 150mm width and 100mm depth. The obtained values are tabulated in following table.

Table 3: Results of flexural strength test.

S.N.	No. of days	Flexural Strength (MPa)			
		0%	0.4%	0.8%	1.6%
1	7	-	3.68	2.70	2.21
2	14	4.17	2.81	3.20	1.47
3	28	4.41	5.01	4.70	2.57

Fig. 3: Variation of hair content vs flexural strength at 7,14 & 28 days.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The experimental results indicate that the inclusion of human hair fiber significantly influences the strength behavior of concrete. Compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength values increased with the addition of hair fibers up to an optimum content of 0.4% by weight of cement. At this dosage, concrete showed maximum 28day compressive strength (24.64 MPa), flexural strength (5.01 MPa) increased by 13.60% of conventional concrete, and improved split tensile strength (3.39 MPa) increased by 5.93% of tensile strength of conventional concrete, demonstrating effective crackbridging and stress transfer

by hair fibers. Lowerthanexpected strength values at 14 days were observed for several specimens, which can be attributed to extreme cold weather conditions that slowed cement hydration during early curing. Once proper curing conditions were ensured, strength gain improved significantly at 28 days, confirming normal hydration behavior. Beyond the optimum fiber content, higher dosages of 0.8% and 1.6% resulted in reduced strength performance. This reduction is mainly due to decreased workability, fiber clustering, and inadequate compaction, which introduced voids and weak zones in the concrete matrix. Overall, the results

confirm that controlled addition of human hair fiber enhances tensile and flexural performance, while excessive fiber content adversely affects concrete strength.

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